

SOME EFFECTIVE METHODS TO TEACH INDONESIAN LANGUAGE IDIOMS

Avazova Feruza Bahodirovna,

The department of the second language senior teacher,
UzSWLU

***Abstract.** Idiom is a number of words which are joined together means something different from the meaning of the words when they stand alone. In order to reproduce the closest natural equivalent in terms of the source context, a translator normally attempts to make adjustments in idioms due to a literal translation of idioms into another language will not make sense. This paper is mainly aimed at finding out how a translator can translate and discover the natural equivalent of English idiomatic expression. The findings show that there are two types of adjustments that are used in translating the idioms. First, by non-figurative expression equivalent and second, by figurative expression equivalent.*

Key words. Adjustments, equivalent, communication situation, constructing knowledge, immense, discover.

Introduction

The Indonesian language, or Bahasa Indonesia, serves as the national language in Indonesia. It is reported to have been successfully adopted as the national language of Indonesia considering the numbers of people who describe themselves as mother tongue speakers of the language

There are 652 local languages spoken across the Indonesian archipelago, so Bahasa Indonesia is the only language that enables all these people to be able to communicate with each other. Because Indonesian is so widely spoken by so many people, the need for good Indonesian to English and English to Indonesian translators is immense. Like many language translations, there are specific challenges that must be overcome for effective translation. Some of these common problems of translation of English to Bahasa and vice versa are outlined below.

Sentence structure

The existence of translation as one aspect of language is very useful and very helpful especially for the people who are from a non native speaker of the source language, in this case English, in order to grasp the meaning or content of that source text easier. Since English text books, one of them is novel have come to Indonesia, translation is needed. Many problems to face in translation, these remind us that many aspects are involved in it including communication situation, cultural context of source language text, lexicon and grammar.

From our experience we can offer some effective tips to teach Indonesian idioms easily.

Students are likely to be passive learners when they receive lecturers only in classrooms. On the contrary, small group discussion could stimulate students to be involved in the active process of constructing knowledge. Furthermore, during group discussions, students will learn from each other, whether consciously or unconsciously. According we applied group discussion in students' active learning of English idioms before explaining the meaning of idioms better than when they were introduced to Indonesian idioms within a story only. This demonstrated the significant effect of group talk on students' understanding of Indonesian idioms.

Idiomatic expressions

Idiomatic expressions are often difficult to translate between any language pair. The further apart the 2 languages are culturally, historically, and linguistically, the more challenging they are to understand or equate. This is particularly important for translators whose work consists of translating text that often has a lot of idiomatic expressions such as literary and marketing translation.

It is clearly described below that when the translator is translating, the first step that must be done is to discover and understand the meaning or the message of the source language text. After discovering the meaning of the source language text, the translator then analyzes and looks for natural form of the receptor/target language.

Eg: This no time to lie down on the job.

Sekarang bukan waktu mengabaikan tugas.

The first step that the translator must analyze is to discover the meaning of the source text. The meaning of the source text at the example above could be grasped that “someone did not pay attention to the job at that time”. After being able to discover the meaning, the next task of the translator is looking for the natural form of the target language which has the same meaning or message as the source language. It will be very different if the translator probably translate it without paying attention to the meaning or message of the source text and just translate it literally, so that the translation will sound unnatural in the target language, for instance: “sekarang bukan waktunya berbaring di atas pekerjaan” that is not commonly used in Indonesian as the target language. So once again, it is emphasized here that in the process of translating, meaning must have priority over the form.

In conclusion Bahasa Indonesia is a very significant language in one of the world’s largest nations by population. English to Indonesian and Indonesian to English translation is important to many businesses, individuals, and private and government agencies and organizations. It’s important to always use professional translators who have an in-depth knowledge of the subtleties of both the Indonesian and English languages.

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